

Truth as Dialogic in Ivan Turgenev's *The Torrents of Spring*

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Those happy years,

Those days so gay,

Like the rush of the spring torrents have vanish'd away

-Old Love- song

Abstract:

The main reason to write this research paper on the Russian writer Ivan Turgenev is to find out the true essence on the late 18th century. The great ideas of these writers was still unknown to the present society. The researcher has tries to pin point the true character of the Russian writers and the influence they had on the modern reader.

Russian literature over the years has been the most delightful for its readers all over the world. This is the richest literature so far as the development of novels are concern. The writers who put forth their words on the papers were the real masters of the world. They were aristocrats, spiritual thinkers, people who worked for the emancipation of serfs and the social workers who saw clearly the then picture of the Russian society. They have witnessed Czar Alexander to the time of Alexander Solzynitsyn. They were responsible for the upliftment of the society and its built on the ideology and the maxims of Society and man as a whole. They were totally and almost every one of them only thought about society, its people and the world therein.

Keywords: Dailogic, realism, emancipation, love.

The present paper focuses on the most truthful of the events that happened in the novel *The Torrents of Spring* by Ivan Turgenev. Turgenev being the most revered artist of the nineteenth century speaks about the absolute truth and realism in the form of stories. The theme of the novel is that of romantic poet in the form of Dimitry Sanin swept into the centre of a whirlpool, yet his infatuation to Gemma remained till the end of his life. This was not an ordinary love affair but of the heroic quality where he actually wins her from her betrothed man. This paper also points out the ideas that made the researcher write this paper. The theme taken is Truth and this truth helps along with the dialogues to come out of the central character

Dimitry Sanin. Being the most westerner of all the writers of his era Turgenev was more of a romantic person. His love affair with Pauline Viardot justifies his story. The memory goes back to the era when Turgenev met Pauline Viardot, French Soprano singer, a married artist falls for the young Ivan. Theirs is the famous love story, this somewhat affected his literary career. But Turgenev was honest and loyal to this woman till the last.

Torrents of Spring ,1871 classic is the turning point in the Russian literature. This novel was in a sense the beginning of a true love, and this very love, to bring a great change in the lovers. These were not ordinary lovers but the passionate ones. They understood each other in every sense and remained so till their last days. This is a true story when Turgenev told Isaac Pavlovski, ' that the entire novel is true. I Personally lived and felt it, It is my own history.' Before beginning with the analysis, the reader wants to clear the term Dialogism: It's something that goes everyday in our life. The nature of it is our consciousness. The itself is dialogic. We can't survive without Dialogues. Human beings are made to express their views, opinions, ideas, express their love and hate, compassion, pity and so on. It is all about responding, agreeing and so on. We perform throughout our life by signalling, with eyes, hands, spirit, and body movement. This is the very fabric of human life. In Bakhtin's words we can say that monologic statements are turned into the dialogues. It needs a dialogic method and a dialogic conception of truth to represent it. Bakhtin refers 'worlds symposium' in his approach to Socratic Dialogues." *That the world has become more and more dialogic.* " *At the base of the genre lies the Socratic notion of...the dialogic nature of human thinking about truth,* " he writes in the Dostoevsky book.

That" *truth is not born nor is it found inside the head of the individual person, it is born between people collectively searching for truth, in the process of his dialogic interaction.* This is a beautiful, touchy and tragic story of a young man of twenty-two, named Dmitry Sanin. He was in Frankfurt, on his way home from Italy to Russia. A he has finished his work and was getting g ready to move to his village, he went to see the beautiful place. It had lovely scenery at Dannecker's Ariadne., visited Goethe's house and was going to Maine. He was already too tired to walk and got dusty, and his boots dusty, and came to a beautiful street and saw a signboard: Giovanni Roselli, Italian confectionery. As Sanin went inside the Patisserie heard strange sound from the next door. The Pattisery he entered was a modest one. Neatly arranged chairs, bottles of biscuits, rusks and chocolates and fruit drops. No one was available there and

suddenly, before Sanin uttered any words, came the voice saying “Is anyone there? ‘And what he saw took his breath away. A girl of nineteen, with beautiful dark curls hanging over her bare shoulders, came into the room, on seeing Sanin rushing seized his hand and said in a breathless voice, Quick, Quick, save him! Hew was enthralled by her beauty and stood still his ground, He had never seen such a beautiful face in his life. The girl again implored him to come, and without any hesitation he went after her. The room he went was a old fashioned and a boy of about fourteen was lying on the sofa having the same features s the girl. He was very pale and white. With closed eyes he looked like a chiselled stone with fine eyebrows. He seemed breathing when the girl perhaps his sister said ,he’s dead, he’s dead. Few minutes ago, we were talking and suddenly he fell down the ground, and started crying loudly. An old man to whom she called Pantaleon came in and told her that he has sent Louis for the doctor. Witnessing the troubled situation again the girl turned to Sanin and told him do something and save him. Sanin had no ideas of medicines. But he thought over it and impromptu asked for some brushes. The girl seemed to be confused but ‘ordered the brushes. Sanin removed the coat and the shirt from the boy’s body. While he was rubbing the boy’s chest the girl sat next to him. In between Sanin glanced at the girl. Great God—what a lovely face!

He noticed that the girl had the most beautiful countenance. Aquiline nose, smooth, and opaque complexion, the glossy hair, with beautiful grey eyes After a long time the young boy started coming to the normalcy. This made the girl’s face transformed. The girl gave a loud cry as she saw her brother breathing. Emile! Emile! The ran to tell her mother this news that her brother is absolutely fine, and the gentleman just visited has cured her dear brother.

Then the real doctor came and checked the boy’s pulse. Everything was fine, seeing the doctor Sanin immediately wen t back to the shop and was about to go , when the appeared before him and asked where he was going? Sanin told her that he was going to Berlin. The girl asked him to come back in the evening and meet her mother. After so many requests Sanin obliged and assured her that he’ll come in the evening. As Sanin came back to the Pattissery he saw the boy was in fine form. Everything was clean. The tablecloth, the coffee-pot with several dishes of biscuits and rolls chocolate carafes of syrup, and the wax candles. All was so beautifully arranged. All the members of the family welcomed and asked about his whereabouts. They were all pleased because he cured their young boy. Pantaleone was very much pleased to hear that his name is Dmitry. The mother was so delighted to see Sanin that she introduced each one

of them to him. Turning towards her daughter She said this is Gemma and the boy is Emile! She told that these were the most obedient of sons. Gemma was all blush when her mother praised her. Every now and then she glanced at Sanin Pantaleon was a baritone singer in opera but later on devoted to the family of Roselli. A good tete-e-tete was going on with the family. This family was a cultured one and when they found out that Sanin belongs to Russia, they insisted him to sing. He sang few songs and this delighted the Roselli family. He then turned to the ladies and asked them to sing, on this Gemma sang various duets and stornelli and delighted her audience. She had one of the sweetest voices he ever heard. Sanin admired her more than her voice. Evening was drawing and Sanin completely forgot in this beautiful family gathering. His excitement was soon noticed by Gemma's mother and told him to wait. He said he had to go to Berlin. As the meeting went far it struck twelve. Sanin was leaving but again Gemma came and informed him that he can't leave for another few days. With smiling and lovely gestures of Gemma Sanin accepted the proposal. Fra Lenore told him that she wants to introduce Gemma's fiancé' Herr Karl, Kluber. The next day Sanin was not ready yet when the servant announced that two people wanted to see him. Here were two people one of them was Emile, and the other Herr Karl Kluber, the fiancé' of the beautiful Gemma. They both thanked Sanin and were happy for everything Sanin did. Herr Kluber was a nobleman. Sanin had to send an urgent letter to Berlin which he did and posted with the help of Pantaleone. And returned to Gemma. Sanin spoke of the Russian life and they were all happy to hear him talk of the great Russia. Gemma most of the time approved what he said. Frau Lenore was an old woman and sickly person. Gemma took great care of her. The bond between them was very lovely.

The next day they planned for a small picnic. Sanin declined first. But on Gemma's insistence he accepted. They were to visit Soden a small town about half an hour distance from Frankfurt. Emile, Herr Kluber, Sanin and Gemma were the only people in the carriage. Soden, lovely place with lovely park and several Wirtchaff beer and coffee parlour. Most of the people visited this place and witnessed bank of Main. Sanin was surprised to see both Gemma and her fiancé'. As the dinner time was approaching fast, Herr Kluber decided to eat and go away. Soon something extraordinary happened that was to take a new turn in the story. At one of the neighbouring table few officers were sitting. They all had been mesmerised by the beauty of Gemma. Suddenly one of them got up and came to the table where Gemma was sitting, plucked

up a rose from Gemma's table Andin aloud voice complemented her on her beauty and said he wants the reward with this flower plucked by her divine fingers. Every one was shocked by this very rude behaviour of the officer. On seeing this Herr Kluber got up and uttered Outrageous! An outrageous liberty! and in great anger asked the waiter to have the bills. Gemma heavily breathing glanced at Herr Kluber. He called her to get up and leave this place immediately. Gemma rose in silence and went with Herr Kluber. This incidence of great insult affected Sanin much. He got up and went to the officer and told him that his behaviour was unworthy and unworthy of the uniform you wear, and told him that he is uncouth. The young officer got angry but his friends cooled him down. He asked whether the girl is his sister, or perhaps her betrothed/ Sanin replied that he is a mere acquaintance of hers. And he is Russian and gave his card and address saying he can find him at the place. With these words he flung a card and picked up Gemma's rose and left the place. This incidence made a great impression on Gemma's mind. The heroicness of Sanin made her love Sanin more than Herr Kluber. Throughout the return journey Gemma was upset by Herr Kluber's behaviour. Sanin really felt sorry for Gemma. But Gemma noticed everything. As the carriage drew near the house Sanin put the rose in her lovely hand and delighted Gemma pressed his hand and went inside the house.

The next day Sanin waited for long time for the officer who insulted Gemma. After a long wait came the officer Herr von Richter. The officer was very arrogant and denied any apology. On this Sanin called him for a duel. The officer accepted the same. In less than two hours the duel will take place between Sanin and Herr Richter. As the officer left the room Sanin sat in his chair and thought what destiny is waiting for him suddenly his life seemed changed and a new turn has taken place. He was in great thoughts when the old man Pantaleone appeared and announced that Emile has told him the whole story. Sanin told him that he is to fight duel with the officer, and he wants a second. Pantaleone accepted gladly to his second. Pantaleone was ready to fight for his benefactors. In the duel each party was to fire twice, with a single-triggered pistol.

As he was getting ready Gemma appeared somewhat distressed and tense.. Sanin tried to console her but she was not listening. Somehow Sanin managed to cheer her up and smilingly Gemma played cards with him till the dinner. As the evening came in Sanin walked in the porch and saw the beautiful sky and its colours. He took the pure air and everything seemed to

him beautiful This total scenery changed his entire life. While walking he heard his name called, "monsieur Dimitri! He ran to see and what did he see? It was Gemma. The sky was cloudless, and the wind became violent, in the transparent light the stars quivered and blew Sanin's hat and also Gemma's curls. Sanin's head was on level with the window-sill and Gemma clutched at his shoulders with both hands, her bosom pressed against his head. This scene lasted for a minute. This havoc and uproar lasted for a minute. When Sanin opened his eyes, he couldn't believe. Her eyes were so immense and so magnificent—such beauty was revealed to him and his heart stopped for a while. Gemma gave him the flower, the rose he captured.

Sanin slept for a long time until Pantaleone knocked the door and told him to be ready for the duel. Soon the carriage was ready. They both went to the duel sight. Herr Richter was late to arrive. The firing began and was missed by both of them. Herr Richter apologised to Sanin and put down the pistol saying he was mistaken. Panatleone shouted the victory. Sanin was disappointed at the result. Emile was delighted to see that Sanin won the duel and shouted for his victory. On returning to the Patisserie, he was welcomed by Frau Lenore and was unhappy for what took place. She told Sanin that Gemma has broken the engagement with Herr Kluber and was in love with Sanin. To, Sanin this was a shock. Frau Lenore told him that Gemma was a strong and hot-headed girl Just like her father, very decisive. Sanin's heart was beating fast as what he is going to answer Gemma. Gemma was in the garden wearing the same hat she wore in Soden. She was picking the sweetest cherries of the season. Gemma was all happy to see Sanin the victorious man. Who fought for the dignity of a woman. She thought him quite heroic and the way he handled the duel. Gemma sent him a letter confessing her love for him and told him to meet her at certain place. As planned Sanin arrived and the walk, the way Gemma clanged to him, and those lovely emotions sprung in him. As he held her lovely hands tears came rolling down Gemma's cheeks, with a smile on her face, a blissful, inaudible laugh. They were both in love for the first time. This was a miracle for both of them. First love, like a revolution to the young hearts. Reaching home Gemma announced that they both loved each other and marry soon. Frau Lenore jumped with joy and came Pantaleoni who was also happy to hear the news. Everywhere happiness was there. The trees, the moon, the stars, whole atmosphere was happy. Frau Lenore was inn despair to melancholy and melancholy to despair. She thought Herr Kluber was a rich man with Eight thousand guilders. Sanin replied that his

estate is in Tula province, with good management would be worth five or six thousand. Gemma convinced her mother regarding the asset. Mother also acknowledged her. She was happy that . Sanin told her that he will go to Russia and sell his estate and come back to Gemma and marry her.. Gemma would be married to the Russian nobility. Everything was decided. Sanin was to go and come back very fast to Gemma. The next day he met his school fellow Polozov. He was very rich this was the time and place that changed entire life of Sanin Gain. This was a twist in the tale. Sanin told him his plans accordingly. And when he found out that Sanin's estate is in Tula Gubernia, he told him to meet Maria Nikolayevna, his wife , who has the entire state in the neighbourhood. On reaching home Sanin told Frau Lenore that he is going to sell his estate to Marya Nikolayevnsa. Gemma also came and sat near him. He told them that within an hour he will leave with his friend in a carriage. He promised that he will write back soon. Both trusted each other. They had full faith and love and honesty between them.

Pavlov told him that his wife runs the estate and it is her own decision he never interferes in her estate. She is the richest lady in the province. They are both announced in the house. After some time, a young beautiful lady in a white silk dress with diamonds on her fingers and round her neck, appeared on the scene. This was Maria Nikolayevna Polozova herself, her luxuriant chestnut hair hanging on either side of her face. Polozov introduced Sanin to her. Maya had a smile, half mocking, gazed Sanin. She was playing with her braids. And walked away leaving a graceful impression of an exquisite neck, marvellous shoulders, and a wonderful waist. This was the first instance Sanin had met with. Sanin was in different frame of mind, all the time remembering Gemma. But this lady's demeanour changed his outlook completely. The way Maria laughed, her style of walk, the playing of her hair and her dimples was altogether strange to Sanin. Sanin found out that Marya is the most powerful and dominating woman and Polozov is a mere puppet in her hands. The behaviour of the lady was quiet embarrassing to Sanin. She asked about his marriage in a strange tone. Sanin replied her neatly. She asked for all his background and Sanin replied her politely. Marya tried to flirt with him. Tossing her head and eyes she murmured that, *'A knight! And after that, believe those who say there are no more idealists left.'* This referred to his heroics in the hotel with Herr Richter. Perhaps she knows what Sanin fought for. There was an argument between two of them Sanin was displeased by the whole affair. The Behaviour of Maria was very strange and appalling. She told him to wait

for three days and come and see her. The thrilling experience Sanin had made him think about this this woman, impossible to acknowledge her body language.

The same night Sanin wrote to his darling Gemma describing her the scenario of polozov's husband and wife. Everything was strange in the house, Polozov and his friends, even the secretary of some embassy, and the man whom he defeated in the duel Here Sanin found out that Marya likes people to do what she likes. She hardly listens to them. She has all the power of the world to control her men. No one escaped, not even Dmitry Sanin. Her spell was beginning to play its trick on Sanin. He was totally under her control. He forgot everything, the letter Gemma wrote, Sanin could not reply it. Pantaleone came to search him and Sanin could not face his anger, He was afraid to see him. Outside the place he saw the devoted Emilio and with him Pantaleone. Sanin's life was full of agony, and humiliation, torments and jealousy. It made him guilty with life poisoned ,with unremitting pain, like the payment of an immense ,incalculable debt(His promise to Gemma). His cup was full.....enough!

In these thirty years passed. He came to Frankfurt and enquired about Gemma, Herr Kluber and the friends he knew. No body knew anything. At last he found the old major Von Donhoff and he learnt that Roselli family has settled in New York. That same day he started writing a letter to Mrs. Gemma asking for forgiveness. And hoped for a answer from Gemma. He described everything that happened and asked forgiveness. He sent the address of the hotel where he was staying. For six whole weeks nothing came. Sanin was sad, at last a letter came with an American stamp from New York. The writing was beautiful. He felt a pang at his heart, when he opened the letter the signature----Gemma was there. Tears came out of eyes. It was a token of forgivance. He unfolded the letter and a photograph fell from it. It was the same photo of Gemma. Those eyes, lips, and the same face. On the other side of the photograph was written my daughter Mariana. Gemma thanked him for writing at last. That she has been married for twenty-seven years and happy with the family. She told that Pantaleon died in Frankfurt and her brother dear Emilio died for his country. Tears came rolling down while reading the letter.

At the end the presenter wishes to conclude that the life was Sanin was a very troublesome and difficult one. He suffered all his life, his mistakes proved to be responsible for his fall. He could not foresee the danger that lied in the character of Marya Ivanovna, and the true love of Gemma remained till Sanin met his death. That before dying at least he was forgiven with great love

and affection by the beautiful Gemma. This is a great lesson in the form of truth in the novel of Ivan Turgenev.

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